

The Impact of Social Media Marketing on Purchase Decision in the Retail Business Industry

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Abstract:

The study aims to examine how social media marketing impacts purchase decisions in the retail business industry and to examine whether social media marketing impacts purchase decisions in the retail industries varies with demographic factors of the users in the Colombo region. The research was conducted with a positivist research philosophy stands using a deductive approach by quantitative method for collecting and analyzing data to gain novel insights. Primary data were gathered through questionnaires from 250 social media marketing consumers from 13 D.S divisions in the Colombo region. Descriptive statistics, correlation, multiple regression, independent sample test and ANOVA are used to analyze the data. The results of the study reveal that peer communication, online advertisement, online network groups and purchase decisions in the retail business have positive relationships. Online advertisements and peer communication highly impact on purchase decisions in the retail business industry in Sri Lanka. Whereas online network groups have a moderate level of impact on purchase decisions in the retail business industry. Overall, social media marketing affects consumer purchasing decisions in a positive way. So, this study's finding helps retail businesses to improve their social media marketing techniques to increase customer preference.

Keywords: *Peer communication, online advertisement, online network groups, Purchase decisions, Retail businesses.*

1. Introduction

Bandara (2021) says Sri Lanka's retail industry is a growth engine. Rapid urbanization has boosted commercial real estate investment during the past decade. Modern companies are replacing tiny, disorderly ones. Many seasoned sellers remain. Modern supermarkets, malls, and convenience stores use even more retail area.

Middle class and demographic developments have also affected shopping. After the civil war ended in 2009, brand-conscious consumers' spending habits changed quickly. Modern transportation and storage investments have improved the island's retail value chain. According to the morning e-newspaper, Colombo's new international-standard stores have improved supply networks and attracted new companies (Dawood, 2021).

Modern grocery stores in Sri Lanka barely represent for 12 to 15% of fast-moving consumer goods sales. According to studies, the rise of supermarkets, clothes stores, shopping Centre, and multinational brands are increasing organized retail penetration in Sri Lanka.

Sri Lanka's retail sector accounts for more than one-third of its GDP. According to information on Sri Lanka's labor force, the sector is crucial for providing jobs as well. 14% of workers were in retail.

2. Research Problem Identification

Social media grew and entered corporate and other human-related areas. Modern corporations demanded social media marketing. social media marketing helps firms to interact with consumers and customers worldwide. Social media users contact businesses more often than ever because of its convenience. Businesses should reach this position to communicate with customers on Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, and Pinterest. It develops a loyal brand, generates leads, and makes money to gain a competitive advantage.

Murdough (2021) says firms may use social media to reach a large clientele in today's technology-driven economy. Social media has changed the ways businesses attract new clients. Businesses can adjust how they devote resources to social media platform development and execution, allowing customers to buy products and services while supporting long-term company goals. It helps competitive firms.

Businesses worldwide, including Sri Lanka, are using internet marketing. E-commerce has overrun the retail industry, inspiring new business owners to create online storefronts. Some e-commerce enterprises have found great success due to 2019's developments. Many industry experts estimate a 5% to 6% growth rate over the next four to five years.

Ahuja and Galvin (2003) say online business has skyrocketed. Many e-retailers have grown in the past decade. These firms compete with each other and traditional stores. New online retailers appear daily. Businesses must assess how social media marketing affects consumer choice to attract website visitors and buyers. New media, unique marketing, and thought are necessary. Despite all of the benefits of the internet, the social marketing sector lacks the capacity to run successful online social marketing initiatives.

Online enterprises have an advantage due to easy media access and cost-effectiveness. During epidemics, most shops sell their brands and products online. There's direct customer-retailer communication. Few companies examine social media marketing's impact on consumer purchases. Online networking, peer-to-peer communication, and advertising affect consumer purchasing. This study looked at online customer buying trends and social media marketing's impact on consumer purchases. This study examines how Sri Lankan consumers view the online retail sector, focusing on social media marketing as a research tool for consumers.

3. Research question

- i. What is the relationship between peer communication and purchase decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka?
- ii. What is the relationship between online advertisement and purchase decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka?
- iii. What is the relationship between online network group and purchase decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka?
- iv. What is the impact of peer communication on purchase decision in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka?
- v. What is the impact of online advertisement on purchase decision in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka?

- vi. What is the impact of online network group on purchase decision in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka?
- vii. What is the impact of social media marketing on Sri Lanka retail businesses?

4. Objectives of the study

- i. To determine the impact of social media marketing on Sri Lanka retail businesses.
- ii. To determine relationships between peer communications, online advertisement, online network groups and purchase decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka.
- iii. To determine the impacts of peer communications, online advertisement, and online network groups on purchase decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka.

5. Literature review

5.1 Social Media Marketing

Social media allow people to connect online, says Golden (2011). The extensive and spontaneous participation in social media activities around a common interest makes them unique. Knowledge sharing and decision-making occur infrequently. Since the audience (consumers) participates, it's interactive and generates real-time content or exchanges. It's interactive and has social media sources (or networking sites). The audience (consumers) adds content or participates in live dialogues.

Social media is an online or electronic platform that promotes engagement, transparency, dialogue, community, and connections. Social media enables individuals to share interests (such music, hobbies, and preferences), voice opinions, and establish profiles with photographs (friends or professional fan pages). Social media platforms include email, chat rooms, blogs, forums, digital music, photographs, and videos.

According to Paquette, social media is a marketing resource (2013). It gives marketers critical data for relationship growth and consumer feedback. Social media marketing is cheap, it permits direct business-to-customer communication. Social media marketing supports conversation, forward-thinking disclosures, and brand respect to improve customer brand relationships.

5.1.1 Dimensions of Social Media Marketing

5.1.1.1 Peer Communication

Consumers can now utilise the Internet to research items, prices, and merchants, according to Akar & Topçu (2011). Since its establishment, the Internet has become more social. No ecosystem can connect different materials. Especially social media has changed how consumers and advertisers interact. (Blogs, forums, and online organisations). Users can produce, edit, and share content on companies, products, and services on social networking sites. Customers think that this data is more trustworthy than a company statement. As a result, the opinions of other people have a big impact on people's purchase decisions.

5.1.1.2 Online Advertisement

Chi-Hui & Kuo-Chang (2017) claim that Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+, YouTube, Pinterest, and Instagram are all used in social network advertising. It's challenging to ignore paid social media ads. Social media is used by 2.5 billion of the 3.2 billion internet users worldwide, and Facebook has 1.9 billion monthly users. Almost all commercial communication plans now include social media. Web ads provide precise product information to consumers. Firms can use this information for interest-based marketing and social media advertising. Social media helps businesses of all sizes locate, engage, and convert customers.

5.1.1.3 Online Network Groups

According to Smith, Menon, and Sivakumar (2005), Online Network Groups, are sections of well-known social media platforms. Users can establish specialised groups to write, debate, and view content. These groups maybe open or closed depending on the owner's preferences and the business's structure. Few studies have examined how Online Network Groups affect purchasing decisions. These groups' help classmates remain in touch. Chiang, Wong, and Huang (2019) Online say customers can meet others with similar needs. Online group buying gives customers a discount when they buy over time. Online group buying allows companies to lower prices, enticing customers to acquire goods and services at a discount. As more individuals buy from retailers' websites online, prices drop. Online group buying helps vendors provide savings to clients. Online group buying increases customer satisfaction, loyalty, and word-of-mouth.

5.2 Social Media Marketing and Customer Purchase Decision

Customers buy market-offered goods and services. Brands offer similar products at different price points to entice consumers. Businesses may use social media to market their goods and product information, saving clients time and increasing online shopping. Dehghani and Tumer (2015) measured customer propensity to buy using Awareness, Consideration, Conversion, Loyalty, and Advocacy. Buying patterns have altered with changing trends. Before buying, buyers prefer to watch reviews. Social media marketing communities increase customer participation and trust in online transactions. Users of the seller establish trust by sharing their knowledge and experiences, which reassures potential purchasers. Perceptions, reasons, learning, attitudes, and beliefs affect customer purchases. Peer-to-peer communication, online advertising, and online network groups affect customers' buying decisions (Gogoi, 2013).

Mintel (2015) reports that buyers rely on peer recommendations while buying. 21% of Irish social media buyers believe their friends' products worked. This study focuses on social media marketing-influenced customer purchasing decisions. They track brand developments and customer buying behaviour. This study analyses how social media marketing affects retail shopper decisions. Buying decisions are a dependent variable in this study. Peer communication, online ads, and network groupings are independent variables. Components and how they affect research variables (Mintel, 2015).

Peer communication is a key way to engage with and sell to clients. Vendors must value peer contact. It encourages consumer trends and internet shopping (Irfan, Rasli, Sulaiman, Sami, & Qureshi, 2019). Peer advertising on social media sites is done by clients. Positive or negative? 83% of internet consumers were ready to buy, according to a poll. This study tests the theory.

H1_a Peer Communication has an impact on Customer Purchase Decision

Odden says brands use advertising to reach consumers (2013). Effective advertising attracts customers. Quality content over quantity affects customers' buying decisions. Online advertising connects brands and customers. Marketing persuasiveness affects consumer behaviour. Proper advertising in text and design structures is needed to maximise the target market's response to the plan. This study examines the hypothesis.

H1_b Online Advertisement has an impact on Customer Purchase Decision

Social media customer or friend referrals improve consumer trust in a brand two times more than the company’s marketing plan (Ludwig, 2013). Online network groups can be positive or detrimental. 73% of online consumers bought goods in a study. Customer reviews can help consumers overcome worries and make online purchases. This study examines the hypothesis.

H1_c Online Network Groups has an impact on Customer Purchase Decision

6. Methodology

6.1 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

6.2 Development of Hypotheses

H ₁	Social media marketing has an impact on Customer Purchase Decision
H _{1a}	Peer Communication has an impact on Customer Purchase Decision
H _{1b}	Online Advertisement has an impact on Customer Purchase Decision
H _{1c}	Online Network Groups has an impact on Customer Purchase Decision

6.3 Sample

6.3.1 Population

Participants of consumers in Colombo district were picked to represent the whole user base.

6.3.2 Sample Selection Procedure

The data gathered during the survey was evaluated using this retrospective evaluation of the Stratified random sampling technique methodology, which was carried out as part of the survey.

6.3.3 Sample Size

The target audience for this study was consumers in the Colombo region who utilize social media to make purchases; a sample size of 250 consumers was chosen for the relevant survey's data gathering needs. Colombo is the major commercial city of Sri Lanka. Also, there are huge number of people are using social media marketing in here than other regions. There are 13 D.S divisions in the Colombo region. 250 consumers were selected as the sample size from the 13 D.S divisions. The majority of the survey's sample size was made up of respondents from the Colombo D.S division, which is 14% of the total sample.

Table 1: Contribution of Sample size

D.S Division	Total Populations	%	Sample contribution
Colombo	330,301	14%	35
Thimbirigasyaya	243,245	10%	26
Dehiwala	90,901	4%	10
Rathmalana	97,587	4%	10
Moratuwa	171,947	7%	18
Kesbewa	250,576	11%	26
Maharagama	200,703	8%	21
Kotte	110,277	5%	12
Kolonnawa	195,864	8%	21
Kaduwela	257,533	11%	27
Homagama	243,089	10%	25
Seethawaka	116,287	5%	12
Seethawaka	66,689	3%	7
TOTAL	2,375,000	100%	250

7. Data presentation and analysis

7.1 Correlation Analysis

The correlation between social media marketing and customer purchase decisions in the retail company area, as shown in the below table 2, was 0.696 overall, indicating a very significant positive association between the two variables. Additionally, the relationship's Sig (P-value) was 0.000 below the 0.01 level. This demonstrated the strength of the association between social media marketing in general and consumer purchasing decisions.

7.1.1 Correlation Analysis of the variables

Dependent variable		Customer purchase decisions		
Correlation considering factors		Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2. tailed)	N
Independent Variables	Peer Communication	0.593**	0.000	250
	Online advertisements	0.776**	0.000	250
	Online network groups	0.396**	0.000	250
Overall	Social media marketing	0.696**	0.000	250

Table 2: Correlations concerning the retail business industry

Correlation is used to show how each independent variable is related to the dependent variable. The correlation coefficient has a range of -1.00 to +1.00. Any value between 0 and 1 indicates a positive relationship. As a result, both variables will increase if the independent variable does, and vice versa. If the value is between -1 and 0, then there is a negative correlation, meaning that the dependent variable would decrease as the independent variable rose and vice versa.

7.2 Regression Analysis

7.2.1 Simple Regression

7.2.1.1 Peer communication and Customer purchase decisions

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.593 ^a	0.352	0.350	0.71444
a. Predictors: (Constant), Peer communication				

Table 3: Model Summary – Peer communication

The correlation coefficient value (R-value), as shown in Table 3 of the model summary table, was 0.593. The R square in this instance was 0.352. In the retail sector, peer communication may account for 35.2% of the variation in customer purchase decisions.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	68.806	1	68.806	134.802	0.000 ^b
	Residual	126.585	248	0.510		
	Total	195.391	249			
Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Decision						
Predictors: (Constant), Peer communication						

Table 4: ANOVA – Peer communication

The F value is 134.802 and the Sig value is 0.000 (less than 0.05), both of which point to a good fit, in accordance with ANOVA table 4. This demonstrated how peer communication may forecast customers’ purchasing decisions with accuracy.

Peer communication affected client purchase decisions by 35.2%, according to the model summary table (3). The ANOVA table was also significant (sig value was 0.000 and less than 0.05). As a

result, the researcher selected the alternative hypothesis proposed by H1a, which holds that peer communication affects customer purchase decisions.

Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.420	0.108		22.369	0.000
	Peer communication	0.348	0.030	0.593	11.610	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Decision

Table 5: Coefficients – Peer communication

Peer communication has a Sig value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, according to table 8 above; as a result, it is a significant variable. Peer communication and client buying decisions can be correlated using the following equation:

$$Y = a + bx$$

$$\text{Customer purchase decision} = 2.420 + 0.348 (\text{Peer communication})$$

7.2.1.2 Online Advertisement and Customer purchase decisions

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.776 ^a	0.603	0.601	0.55951
a. Predictors: (Constant), Online Advertisement				

Table 6: Model Summary – Online Advertisement

The correlation coefficient value (R-value), as shown in Table 5 of the model summary table, was 0.776. The R square in this instance was 0.603. The diversity in consumer purchasing decisions in the retail sector might be explained by online advertising to the tune of 60,3%.

ANOVA ^a						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	117.755	1	117.156	376.156	0.000 ^b
	Residual	77.636	248	0.313		
	Total	195.391	249			
c. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Decision						
d. Predictors: (Constant), Online Advertisement						

Table 1: ANOVA – Online Advertisement

The F value is 117.755 and the Sig value is 0.000 (less than 0.05), both of which point to a good fit, in accordance with ANOVA table 10. This demonstrated how effectively online advertising forecasts consumer purchasing decisions. Online advertisements influenced consumer purchase decisions by 60.3%, according to the model summary table (6). The ANOVA table was also significant (sig value was 0.000 and less than 0.05).

In light of this, the researcher chose the H1_b alternative hypothesis, which contends that online advertising influences consumers' purchase decisions.

Coefficients ^a				
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.

		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.903	0.142		6.382	0.000
	Online Advertisement	0.740	0.038	0.776	19.395	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Decision						

Table 8: Coefficients – Online Advertisement

Online advertisement has a Sig value of 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05, as seen in table 7 above; as such, it is a significant variable. Online advertisements and consumer purchase decisions can be correlated using the following equation:

$$Y = a + bx$$

$$\text{Customer purchase decision} = 0.903 + 0.740 (\text{Online Advertisement})$$

7.2.1.3 Online Network Groups and Customer purchase decisions

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.396 ^a	0.157	0.153	0.81512
a. Predictors: (Constant), Online Network Groups				

Table 9: Model Summary – Online Network Groups

The correlation coefficient value (R-value), as shown in Table 8 of the model summary table, was 0.396. The R square in this instance was 0.157. Online network groups may account for 15.7% of the variation in consumer purchasing behaviour in the retail sector.

ANOVA^a						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	30.614	1	30.614	46.077	0.000 ^b
	Residual	164.777	248	0.664		
	Total	195.391	249			
e. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Decision						

f. Predictors: (Constant), Online Network Groups

Table:10 ANOVA – Online Network Groups

The F value is 46.077 and the Sig value is 0.000 (less than 0.05), all of which point to a good fit, in accordance with ANOVA table 9. This demonstrated how Online Network Groups can forecast consumer purchase behaviour with accuracy. Online Network Groups influenced consumer purchase decisions by 15.7%, as shown in the model summary table (8). The ANOVA table was also significant (sig value was 0.000 and less than 0.05). The researcher then accepted the H1c alternative hypothesis, which contends that Online Network Groups have an effect on Consumer Purchase Decisions.

Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.051	0.228		8.979	0.000
	Online Network Groups	0.400	0.059	0.396	6.788	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Decision

Table 2: Coefficients – Online Network Groups

Online Network Groups is a significant variable since, as shown in table 10 above, the Sig value of Online Advertisement was 0.000, which was less than 0.05. Online network groups and consumer purchasing behaviour can be correlated using the following equation,

$$Y = a + bx$$

$$\text{Customer purchase decision} = 2.051 + 0.400 (\text{Online Network Groups})$$

7.2.1.4 Social media marketing and Customer purchase decisions

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.696 ^a	0.484	0.482	0.63747
a. Predictors: (Constant), Online Network Groups				

Table 3: Model Summary – Social media marketing

The model summary table (Table 11) shows that the social media marketing correlation \ coefficient value (R-value) was 0.696. In this instance, the R square value was 0.484. This clarified why social media marketing in Sri Lanka’s retail sector could only account for 48.4% of the variation in customer purchase decisions.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	94.612	1	94.612	232.822	0.000 ^b
	Residual	100.780	248	0.406		
	Total	195.391	249			
g. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Decision						
h. Predictors: (Constant), Social media marketing						

Table 4: ANOVA – Social media marketing

The ANOVA table shows that the F value is 232.822 and the Sig value is 0.000, both of which point to a robust match (10). This demonstrated how social media marketing may forecast customer purchase decisions with accuracy. The model summary table (12) shows that social

media marketing had a 48.4% influence on consumer purchase decisions. The ANOVA table was

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.237	0.158		7.845	0.000
	Social media marketing	0.655	0.043	0.696	15.259	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Decision

also significant (sig value was 0.000 and less than 0.05). The alternative hypothesis put out by H1 that social media marketing affects customers' purchase decisions were adopted as a result.

The Sig value for social media marketing was 0.000, which was smaller than 0.05, as shown in table 13 above; as a result, it is a significant variable. The following equation can be used to determine the relationship between social media marketing and consumer purchasing decisions:

$$Y = a + bx$$

$$\text{Customer purchase decision} = 1.237 + 0.655 (\text{social media marketing})$$

Table 5: Coefficients – Social media marketing

7.2.2 Multiple Regression

Using multiple linear regressions, the study found that social media marketing has an effect on customers' purchase decisions. All three independent variables were considered by the researcher to ascertain what factors affected customer purchasing decisions.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.830 ^a	0.690	0.686	0.49651
a. Predictors: (Constant), Peer communications, Online advertisements, Online network groups				

Table 6: Multiple Regressions - Model Summary

According to the model summary table (Table 14), The R-value is 0.830 based on the results of the numerous correlation coefficients. The R square value in this case was 0.690. This indicates how peer communications, online advertisements, and online network groups account for 69.0% of the variation in customer purchase decisions in the retail business sector. The diversity of client buying decisions could be explained by a wide range of other factors. In other words, 31.0% of the variety in consumer purchase decisions cannot be explained by peer communications, online marketing, or online network groupings. There can be additional elements that affect consumer buying choices.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	134.746	3	44.915	182.194	0.000 ^b
	Residual	60.645	246	0.247		
	Total	195.391	249			
a. Dependent Variable: OCB						
a. Predictors: (Constant), Peer communications, Online advertisements, Online network groups						

Table 15: Multiple Regressions – ANOVA

The Sig value was 0.000, as shown by the ANOVA table (15). (P-value less than 0.01). The F value of 134.746 showed a good fit. This indicated that by combining these factors, it could be possible to accurately forecast what customers will buy.

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.345	0.177		17.543	0.000
Peer communications	0.424	0.082	0.443	18.246	0.000
Online advertisements	0.558	0.094	0.578	19.992	0.000
Online Network Groups	0.124	0.043	0.143	13.357	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Decisions

Table 7: Multiple Regressions – Coefficients

All of the variables were important determinants of customer purchase decisions in the retail sector.

All variables were smaller than (Sig Value of Peer Communications = 0.000, Sig Value of Online Ads = 0.000, and Sig Value of Online Network Groups = 0.000). The variable for online advertisements had the greatest Beta value of all the variables (Beta value of development behaviour = 0.578). Online advertisements are the most important social media marketing aspect influencing customer purchase decisions in the banking industry, the researcher determined. Following is a general overview of how online marketing, peer communications, and online network groups affect consumer purchase decisions in the retail sector.

$$Y = a + b_{x1} + b_{x2} + b_{x3}$$

$$CPD = 1.345 + 0.424 PC + 0.558 OA + 0.124 ONG$$

Where,

PC = Peer Communications

OA = Online Advertisements

ONG = Online Network Groups

8. Conclusions and Recommendation.

8.1 Conclusions

H₁: Social media marketing has an impact on Customer Purchase Decisions.

In light of the facts, the researcher has decided to adopt the alternative hypothesis of H₁, "Social media marketing having an impact on Customer Purchase Decisions." The main objective of the study was to "assess the impact of social media marketing on Sri Lankan retail firms." The study concluded that social media marketing has a positive impact on consumer purchasing behaviour in Sri Lanka's retail sector by proving the first hypothesis' viability.

This study found a positive association between social media marketing and purchasing decisions, which is consistent with prior studies. For instance, Hasan, Haq, and Rahman (2019) examined the use of social media marketing by 400 college and university students in Dhaka when making purchases. The study discovered, with a 95% degree of confidence, a favourable association between social media marketing and purchasing decisions. Ansari, Ghori, Kazi, and Ansari (2019) conducted a study with 250 online buyers in Hyderabad to examine the relationship between social media marketing, brand awareness, and purchase behaviour. According to the study, there is a strong and positive association between social media marketing and consumer behaviour ($r = .0773, p.000$).

According to Jindoliya (2017), social media marketing and purchasing decisions had a positive correlation of 0.557, which was less than 0.05. Thus, Jindoliya (2017) established a significant relationship between social media marketing and the purchasing decisions made by Navi Mumbai inhabitants between the ages of 24-35 with a 95% confidence level. This led to the conclusion that broadening the use of social media marketing will positively affect consumers' purchasing decisions.

H_{1a}: Peer communication has an impact on Customer Purchase Decisions.

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The findings support the alternative interpretation of H1a, which claims that "peer communication affects customer purchasing decisions." The main objective of the study was to "evaluate the influence of peer communication on purchasing decisions in the Sri Lankan retail business industry," as well.

By proving the second hypothesis, the researcher got to the conclusion that peer communication influences consumer purchase decisions in Sri Lanka's retail business sector favorably. The results of this study, which demonstrated a favorable relationship between peer communication and purchase choices, were consistent with earlier investigations. For instance, Hasan, Haq, and Rahman's (2019) examination of the link between peer communication and purchasing decisions included 400 college and university students from Dhaka. The study discovered a positive association between peer communication and purchasing decisions with a 95% confidence interval.

In an investigation by Armagan & Cetin (2013) to determine the relationship between peer communication and purchasing decisions, 400 clients in the Adnan Menderes University neighborhood took part. The study found a favorable and substantial relationship between peer communication and purchasing decisions ($r = 0.693$, $p.000$). Wanga, Yu, and Wei found a positive association between peer communication and purchasing decisions of 0.518, less than 0.05. (2012).

Wanga, Yu, and Wei (2012) discovered a substantial association between peer communication and purchasing choices among 292 people who took part in peer communication about products via social media, with a 95% confidence level. It was concluded as a result that enhancing peer communication in all of its forms will assist clients in making more informed purchasing choices.

H1b: Online advertisement has an impact on Customer Purchase Decisions.

In light of the findings, the researcher has decided to accept the alternative H1b hypothesis, which claims that "online advertisement has an impact on Customer Purchase Decisions." The second specific objective of the study was to, among other things, "evaluate the influence of internet advertisement on purchase decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka." The third

hypothesis was proved, leading the researcher to the finding that online advertising positively affects consumer purchase decisions in Sri Lanka's retail business sector.

This study's findings, which showed a favorable correlation between internet advertising and purchasing behaviour, were consistent with those of earlier investigations. For instance, Hasan, Haq, and Rahman (2019) investigated the connection between 400 college and university students in Dhaka city's buying decisions and internet advertising. The researcher discovered a strong correlation between internet advertising and purchasing choices, with a 95% confidence interval.

Hilda (2019) conducted study to examine the relationship between online advertising and purchasing behaviour, paying close attention to staff employees in the administration of Kenya's top five (5) online shopping sites. According to the study, there is a substantial and favorable correlation between online advertisements and buying behaviour ($r = 0.553$, $p .000$). Cinar & Enginkaya found a 0.553 positive connection between online advertisements and buying decisions, which was less than 0.05. (2014). With a 95% confidence level, Cinar & Enginkaya (2014) concluded that there was a significant relationship between online advertising and purchasing choices among 475 people who made purchases online. It was determined that broadening online advertising would enhance customers' purchasing decisions.

H_{1c}: Online network groups have an impact on Customer Purchase Decisions.

In light of the evidence, the researcher has decided to accept the alternative H_{1c} hypothesis, which claims that "online network groupings have an impact on client purchasing decisions." Determine "the influence of the online network on purchasing decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka" was the third specific aim of the study. The fourth hypothesis was proved, leading the researcher to the finding that online network groups positively affect consumer purchasing decisions in Sri Lanka's retail industry.

This study's findings, which showed a favorable correlation between online network group membership and purchasing behaviour, were consistent with those of earlier investigations. For instance, Hasan, Haq, and Rahman (2019) investigated the connection between 400 college and university students in Dhaka cities online network groups and their buying decisions. The researcher discovered a favorable association between online network groups and purchasing choices with a 95% degree of confidence.

Yogesh & Yesha (2014) studied 150 consumers to see how online network groupings and purchase behaviour interacted. The results of the study show that there is a high and positive link between online network groups and consumer behaviour ($r = 0.453$, $p.000$). Cinar & Enginkaya (2014) discovered a positive connection between online network groups and purchasing behaviour that was smaller than 0.05, with a value of 0.553.

With a 95% confidence level, Cinar & Enginkaya (2014) came to the conclusion that there was a significant association between online network groups and the purchasing choices of 475 participants who made online purchases. This led to the conclusion that larger online network groupings and their dimensions would have a greater positive impact on consumers' purchase decisions.

This study's main objective is to "identify the most influential social media marketing component impacting purchase decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka," in addition to analyzing hypotheses. This objective was achieved via multiple regression analysis. The "online advertisements" dimension's beta value of 0.578 was the highest of all the standardized coefficients. Online advertising, according to the researcher, is the most significant social media marketing factor affecting consumer purchase decisions in Sri Lanka's retail business sector.

8.2 Recommendations

The study's findings indicate that real-time customer feedback, online newsletters, online competitions, and loyalty rewards programmes are all favorably received by consumers. The retail sector would need to hire a team of specialists to monitor consumer-brand interactions on social media. The retail business sector claims that appealing to both men and women between the ages of 26 and 33 is how current newsletters, press releases, and well-executed ad hoc competitions "attract" customers. Customers' social media incentives should be clearly acknowledged in the retail sector.

Creating a marketing strategy to increase retail's use of social media and increasing traffic to the retailer's social media profiles. The events ought to raise brand recognition, establish the company's reputation, and generate conversation online. To get them to take part in the campaign,

consumers must be persuaded. In order to strengthen the bond between the consumer and the brand and encourage successful customer contact, the campaign should be interactive. The retail industry will learn fresh information about its target markets as a result.

According to the research analysis in chapter five, the preferred social media platform for the retail company industry is online advertising. Online advertisement has a major positive impact on purchase decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka. According to research, Facebook and Twitter are used by the vast majority of respondents. Therefore, Facebook and Twitter should be used in their advertising.

Peer communication has a weak positive impact on purchase decisions in the retail business industry of Sri Lanka. Users can keep an eye on the development and performance of their accounts by using the analytics offered by social media networks. This entails looking at daily visits, likes per remark, and daily comments on social media networks like Facebook and Twitter. The retail industry needs enough funds to create unique designs for fan pages (production costs), create entertaining games, and maintain fans on social media. For a brand to connect with consumers through social media, real-time feedback and continual monitoring are crucial. As a result, the retail industry must make sure that adequate funds are allocated for "communicating" and "engaging" with clients on social media. The retail sector has to choose which analytical techniques will give the best key performance and investment return indicators.

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